

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING SCIENCES & RESEARCH
TECHNOLOGY

A COMMON FIXED POINT THEOREM ON FUZZY 3-METRIC SPACES

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DOI:

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we prove a common fixed point theorem for four mappings on fuzzy 3-metric spaces. Our result is an extension of results of S. H. Cho [2] to fuzzy 2-metric spaces. Also, it is a generalization of a result of S. Sharma [11].

INTRODUCTION

The concept of fuzzy sets was introduced by L. A. Zadeh [13] in 1965. To use this concept in topology and analysis, many authors have extensively developed the theory of fuzzy sets and applications. With the concept of fuzzy sets, the fuzzy metric space was introduced by I. Kramosil and J. Michalek [8] in 1975. M. Grabiec [5] proved the contraction principle in fuzzy metric spaces in 1988. Moreover, A. George and P. Veeramani [4] modified the notion of fuzzy metric spaces with the help of t -norms in 1994. G. Aähler [3] investigated 2-metric spaces in a series of his papers. Sharma, Sharma and Iseki [12] investigated, for the first time, contraction type mappings in 2-metric spaces. Many authors have studied common fixed point theorems in fuzzy metric spaces. Some of interesting papers are Y. J. Cho [1], George and Veeramani [4], Grabiec [5], Kramosil and Michalek [8] and S. Sharma [11]. S. H. Cho [2] proved a common fixed point theorem for four mappings in fuzzy metric spaces and S. Sharma [11] proved a common fixed point theorem for three mappings in fuzzy 2-metric spaces. In this paper we prove a common fixed point theorem for four mappings in fuzzy 2-metric spaces. Our theorem is an extension of results of S. H. Cho [2] to fuzzy 3-metric spaces. And also, it is a generalization of result of and S. Sharma [11].

PRELIMINARIES

Now we begin with some definitions:

Definition (2 A): A binary operation $*$: $[0, 1] \times [0,1] \times [0,1] \times [0,1] \rightarrow [0,1]$ is called a continuous t -norm if $([0,1], *)$ is an abelian topological monoid with unit 1 such that $a_1 * b_1 * c_1 * d \geq a_2 * b_2 * c_2 * d_2$ whenever $a_1 \geq a_2, b_1 \geq b_2, c_1 \geq c_2$ and $d_1 \geq d_2$ for all $a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, c_1, c_2$ and d_1, d_2 are in $[0,1]$.

Definition (2 B): The 3-tuple $(X, M, *)$ is called a fuzzy 3-metric space if X is an arbitrary set, $*$ is continuous t -norm and M is fuzzy set in $X^4 \times [0, \infty)$ satisfying the followings

$$(FM'' - 1): M(x, y, z, w, 0) = 0$$

$$(FM'' - 2): M(x, y, z, w, t) = 1, \forall t > 0$$

$$(FM'' - 3): M(x, y, z, w, t) = M(x, w, z, y, t) = M(z, w, x, y, t) = \dots \quad (FM'' - 4): M(x, y, z, w, t_1 + t_2 + t_3) \geq M(x, y, z, u, t_1) * M(x, y, u, w, t_2) * M(x, u, z, w, t_3) * M(x, y, z, w, t_4)$$

Definition (2 C): Let $(X, M, *)$ be a fuzzy 3-metric space. A sequence $\{x_n\}$ in fuzzy 3-metric space X is said to be convergent to a point $x \in X$,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} M(x_n, x, a, b, t) = 1, \text{ for all } a, b \in X \text{ and } t > 0$$

A sequence $\{x_n\}$ in fuzzy 3-metric space X is called a Cauchy sequence, if

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} M(x_{n+p}, x_n, a, b, t) = 1, \text{ for all } a, b \in X \text{ and } t, p > 0$$

A fuzzy 3-metric space in which every Cauchy sequence is convergent is said to be complete.

Definition (2 D): A function M is continuous in fuzzy 3-metric space, iff whenever for all $a \in X$ and $t > 0$.

$$x_n \rightarrow x, y_n \rightarrow y, \text{ then } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} M(x_n, y_n, a, b, t) = M(x, y, a, t), \forall a, b \in X \text{ and } t > 0$$

Definition (2 E): Two mappings A and S on fuzzy 3-metric space X are weakly commuting iff $M(ASu, SAu, a, b, t) \geq M(Au, Su, a, t), \forall u, a, b \in X$ and $t > 0$.

Definition (2 F): Self mappings A and B of a fuzzy 3 metric space (X, M, Δ) is said to be compatible, if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} M(ABx_n, BAx_n, a, t) = 1$ for all $a \in X$ and $t > 0$, whenever $\{x_n\}$ is a sequence in X such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Ax_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Bx_n = z$ for some $z \in X$.

MAIN RESULT

Lemma 3.1. $M(x, y, z, w, \cdot)$ is non-decreasing for all $x, y, z, w \in X$.

Proof. Let $s, t > 0$ be any points such that $t > s$. Then $t = s + \frac{t-s}{2} + \frac{t-s}{2}$.

Hence we have

$$M(x, y, z, w, t) = M\left(x, y, z, w, s + \frac{t-s}{2} + \frac{t-s}{2}\right) \geq \Delta M(x, y, z, w, s), M\left(x, y, z, w, \frac{t-s}{2}\right), M(x, y, z, w, \frac{t-s}{2}) = M(x, y, z, w, s)$$

Thus, $M(x, y, z, w, t) > M(x, y, z, w, s)$

From now on, let (X, M, Δ) be a fuzzy 2 – metric space with the following condition :

$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} M(x, y, z, w, t) = 1$ for all $x, y, z, w \in X$.

Lemma 3.2. Let (X, M, Δ) be a fuzzy 3-metric space. If there exists $q \in (0,1)$ such that $M(x, y, z, w, qt + 0) \geq M(x, y, z, w, t)$ for all $x, y, z, w \in X$.

with $w \neq x, w = y, w \neq z$ and $t > 0$ then $x = y = z$.

Proof. Since $M(x, y, z, w, t) \geq M(x, y, z, w, qt + 0) \geq M(x, y, z, w, t)$ for all $t > 0$, $M(x, y, z, w, \cdot)$ is constant. Since $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} M(x, y, z, w, t) = 1$, for all $t > 0$. Hence, $x = y = z$. because $w \neq x, w = y, w \neq z$.

Lemma 3.3. Let (X, M, Δ) be a fuzzy 3-metric space, and let

$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = x, \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} y_n = y, \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} u_n = u, \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} v_n = v$, Then the followings are satisfied .

(1) $\liminf M(x_n, y_n, a, b, t) \geq M(x, y, a, b, t)$ for all $a, b \in X$ and $t \geq 0$.

(2) $M(x, y, a, b, t + 0) \geq \limsup M(x_n, y_n, a, b, t)$ $a, b \in X$ and $t > 0$.

Proof. (1) For all $a, b \in X$ and $t > 0$; we have

$$\begin{aligned} M(x_n, y_n, a, b, t) &\geq \Delta(M(x_n, x, a, b, t), M(x_n, y_n, x, y, t); M(y_n, x, a, b, t)) \\ &\geq \Delta(M(x_n, x, a, b, t), M(x_n, x, y_n, a, t), M(y_n, y, a, b, t), M(x, y, a, b, t), M(y_n, x, y, t)) \end{aligned}$$

which implies

$$\liminf M(x_n, y_n, a, b, t) \geq \Delta(1, 1, 1, M(x, y, a, b, t), 1) = M(x, y, a, b, t)$$

for all $a, b \in X$ and $t > 0$.

(2) Let $\varepsilon > 0$ be given. For all $a, b \in X$ and $t > 0$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} M(x, y, a, b, t + 2\varepsilon) &\geq \Delta\left(M\left(x, x_n, a, b, \frac{\varepsilon}{2}\right), M(x_n, y, a, b, t + \varepsilon), M\left(x, y, x_n, a, \frac{\varepsilon}{2}\right)\right) \\ &\geq \Delta\left(M\left(x_n, x, a, b, \frac{\varepsilon}{2}\right), M\left(x_n, x, y, a, \frac{\varepsilon}{2}\right), M(x_n, y_n, a, b, t), M\left(x_n, y, y_n, a, \frac{\varepsilon}{2}\right), M\left(y_n, y, a, b, \frac{\varepsilon}{2}\right)\right) \end{aligned}$$

which implies $M(x, y, a, b, t + 2\varepsilon) \geq \limsup M(x_n, y_n, a, b, t)$. Letting $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ in the above inequality, we have $M(x, y, a, b, t + 0) \geq \limsup M(x_n, y_n, a, b, t)$.

Note that for all $a, b \in X$ and $t > 0$; in general the inequality

$M(x, y, a, b, t) \geq \limsup M(x_n, y_n, a, b, t)$. is not true, because $M(x, y, z, w, \cdot)$ is left continuous (in general, not right continuous).

Lemma 3.4. Let (X, M, Δ) be a fuzzy 3-metric space and let A and B be continuous self mappings of X and $[A;B]$ be compatible. Let x_n be a sequence in X such that $Ax_n \rightarrow Az$ and $Bx_n \rightarrow Bz$ Then $ABx_n \rightarrow Az$.

Proof. Since A, B are continuous maps, $ABx_n \rightarrow Az$, $Bx_n \rightarrow Bz$ and so, $M\left(ABx_n, Az, a, b, \frac{t}{3}\right)$ and $M\left(Bx_n, Bz, a, b, \frac{t}{3}\right) \rightarrow 1$ for all $a, b \in X$ and $t > 0$: Since the pair $[A, B]$ is compatible, $\left(Bx_n, AB, a, b, \frac{t}{3}\right) \rightarrow 1$ for all $a, b \in X$ and $t > 0$: Thus, $M(ABx_n, Bz, a, t) \geq \Delta\left(M\left(ABx_n, Bz, ABx_n, a, \frac{t}{3}\right), M\left(ABx_n, Bx_n, a, b, \frac{t}{3}\right), M\left(Bx_n, Bz, a, b, \frac{t}{3}\right)\right) \geq \Delta\left(M\left(Bx_n, Bz, ABx_n, a, \frac{t}{3}\right), M\left(Bx_n, ABx_n, a, b, \frac{t}{3}\right), M\left(Bx_n, Bz, a, b, \frac{t}{3}\right)\right) \rightarrow 1$ $a, b \in X$ and $t > 0$. Hence, $ABx_n \rightarrow Bz$.

Theorem 3.5. Let (X, M, Δ) be a complete fuzzy 2-metric space with continuous t -norm Δ of H -type, and let S and T be continuous self mappings of X . Then S and T have a unique common fixed point in X if and only if there exist two self mappings A, B of X satisfying

- (1) $AX \subseteq TX, BX \subseteq SX$
- (2) the pair $[A, S]$ and $[B, T]$ are compatible,
- (3) there exists $q \in (0, 1)$ such that for every $x, y, a, b \in X$ and $t > 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} & M(Ax, By, a, b, qt) \\ & \geq \{\min M(Sx, Ty, a, b, t), M(Ax, Sx, a, b, t), M(By, Ty, a, b, t), M(Ax, Ty, a, b, t)\}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.0)$$

Indeed, A, B, S and T have a unique common fixed point in X .

Proof. Suppose that S and T have a (unique) common fixed point, say $z \in X$. Define $A : X \rightarrow X$ by $Ax = z$ for all $x \in X$, and $B : X \rightarrow X$ by $Bx = z$ for all $x \in X$. Then one can see that (1)- (3) are satisfied. Conversely, assume that there exist two self mappings A, B of X satisfying conditions (1)- (3). From condition (1) we can construct two sequences $\{x_n\}$ and $\{y_n\}$ of X such that $y_{2n-1} = Tx_{2n-1} = Ax_{2n-2}$ and $y_{2n} = Sx_{2n} = Bx_{2n-1}$ for $n = 1, 2, \dots$. Putting $x = x_{2n}$ and $y = x_{2n+1}$ in (3.0), we have that for all $a \in X$ and $t > 0$. In general, we obtain that for all $a \in X, t > 0$ and $n = 1, 2, \dots$

$$M(y_n, y_{n+1}, a, b, qt), M(y_n, 1, y_n, a, b, t). \text{ Thus, for all } a \in X, t > 0 \text{ and } n = 1, 2, \dots \dots$$

$$M(y_n, y_{n+1}, a, b, t) \geq M\left(y_0, y_1, a, b, \frac{q}{t^n}\right). \quad (3.1)$$

We now show that $\{y_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in X . Let $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ be given. Since the t -norm Δ is of H -type, there exists $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ such that for all $m, n \in N$ with $m > n \Delta^{2^{m-n}}(1 - \lambda) > (1 - \varepsilon)$. (3.2)

Since $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} M\left(y_0, y_1, a, b, \frac{q}{t^n}\right) = 1$, there exists $n_0 \in N$ such that for all $a, b \in X$ and $t > 0$ with $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} M\left(y_0, y_1, a, b, \frac{q}{t^n}\right) = 1$, for all n, n_0 From (3.1) we have that for all $a, b \in X$ and $t > 0$,

$$M(y_n, y_{n+1}, a, b, t) > 1 - \lambda, \text{ for all } n, n_0.$$

Let $m > n \geq n_0$. Then for all $a, b \in X$ and $t > 0$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} M(y_m, y_n, a, b, t) & \geq \Delta(M(y_{n+1}, y_n, a, b, 3^{-1}t), \Delta(M(y_{n+1}, y_n, y_m, a, 3^{-1}t), M(y_{n+1}, y_m, a, b, 3^{-1}t))) \\ & \geq \Delta\left(\Delta^2((1 - \lambda), M(y_{n+1}, y_m, a, b, 3^{-1}t))\right) \dots \dots \dots (3:3) \end{aligned}$$

Since $M(y_{n+1}, y_n, a, b, 3^{-2}t) \geq \Delta(M(y_{n+2}, y_{n+1}, a, b, 3^{-2}t), \Delta(M(y_{n+2}, y_{n+1}, y_m, a, 3^{-2}t), M(y_{n+2}, y_m, a, b, 3^{-2}t)))$. from (3.3) we get

$$M(y_m, y_n, a, b, t) \geq \Delta\left(\Delta^{2^2}(1 - \lambda), M(y_{n+2}, y_m, a, b, 3^{-2}t)\right).$$

Inductively, we obtain

$$M(y_m, y_n, a, b, t) \geq \Delta\left(\Delta^{2^{m-n}}(1 - \lambda), M(y_m, y_n, a, b, 3^{n-m}t)\right) = \Delta^{2^{m-n}}(1 - \lambda) \dots \dots \dots (3.4)$$

From (3.2) and (3.4) we get for all $a, b \in X$ and $t > 0$ $M(y_m, y_n, a, b, t) > 1 - \varepsilon$ for $m > n \geq n_0$. Thus $\{y_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence.

It follows from completeness of X that there exists $z \in X$ such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} y_n = z$. Hence $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} y_{2n-1} = Tx_{2n-1} = Ax_{2n-2} = z$.

From Lemma 3.4, $ASx_{2n-1} = Sz$ and $BTx_{2n-1} = Tz \dots \dots \dots (3.5)$
Meanwhile, for all $a \in X$ with $a \neq Sz$ and $a \neq Tz$, and $t > 0$

$$\geq \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} M(ASx_{2n+1}, BTx_{2n+1}, a, b, qt) \\ M(SSSx_{2n+1}, TTSx_{2n+1}, a, b, t), M(ASSx_{2n+1}, SSSx_{2n+1}, a, b, t), M(BTx_{2n+1}, TTx_{2n+1}, a, b, t), \\ M(ASx_{2n+1}, TTx_{2n+1}, a, b, t) \end{array} \right\}$$

Taking limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$, and using (3:5), and Lemma 3.5, we have for all $a \in X$ with $a \neq Sz$ and $a \neq Tz$, and $t > 0$

$$\geq \min \{ M(Sz, Tz, a, b, qt + 0), M(Sz, Tz, a, b, t), M(Sz, Sz, a, b, t), M(Tz, Tz, a, b, t), M(Sz, Tz, a, b, t), M(Sz, Tz, a, b, t) \}$$

By Lemma 3.2, we have $Sz = Tz \dots \dots \dots$ (3.6)

From (3.0) we get for all $a \in X$ with $a \neq Sz$ and $a \neq Tz$, and $t > 0$

$$\geq \min \{ M(Az, BTx_{2n+1}, a, b, qt), M(Sz, TTx_{2n+1}, a, t), M(Az, Sz, a, b, t), M(BTx_{2n+1}, TTx_{2n+1}, a, b, t), M(Az, TTxx_{2n+1}, a, b, t) \}$$

Taking limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$, and using (3:5), (3:6) and Lemma 3.3,

$$\geq \min \{ M(Az, Tz, a, b, qt + 0), M(Sz, Tz, a, b, t), M(Az, Sz, a, b, t), M(Tz, Tz, a, b, t), M(Az, Tz, a, b, t) \}$$

$$\geq M(Az, Tz, a, b, t).$$

By Lemma 3.2, $Az = Tz \dots \dots \dots$ (3.7)

and for all $a \in X$ with $a \neq Sz$ and $a \neq Tz$, and $t > 0$

$$\geq \min \{ M(Az, BTx_{2n+1}, a, b, qt), M(Sz, Tz, a, b, t), M(Az, Sz, a, b, t), M(Bz, Tz, a, b, t), M(Az, Tz, a, b, t) \}$$

$$\geq \min \{ M(Tz, Tz, a, b, t), M(Tz, Tz, a, b, t), M(Bz, Az, a, b, t), M(Tz, Tz, a, b, t) \}$$

$$\geq M(Az, Bz, a, b, t).$$

By Lemma 3.2, $Az = Bz \dots \dots \dots$ (3.8)

It follows that $Az = Bz = Sz = Tz$.

For all $a \in X$ with $a \neq Bz$ and $a \neq z$, and $t > 0$

$$\geq \min \{ M(Ax_{2n}, Bz, a, b, qt), M(Sx_{2n}, Tz, a, b, t), M(Ax_{2n}, Sx_{2n}, a, b, t), M(Bz, Tz, a, b, t), M(Ax_{2n}, Tz, a, b, t) \}$$

Taking limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$, and using (3.5), and Lemma 3.3, we have for

all $a \in X$ with with $a \neq Bz$ and $a \neq z$, and $t > 0$

$$\geq \min \{ M(z, Tz, a, b, t), M(z, z, a, b, t), M(Bz, Bz, a, b, t), M(z, Tz, a, b, t) \} \geq M(z, Tz, a, b, t) \geq M(z, Bz, a, b, t)$$

and so we have $M(z, Bz, a, b, qt) \geq M(z, Bz, a, b, t)$, and hence $Bz = z$.

Thus $z = Az = Bz = Sz = Tz$, and so z is a common fixed point of A, B, S and T .

For uniqueness, let w be another common fixed point of A, B, S and T .

Then, for all $a \in X$ with with $a \neq z$ and $a \neq w$, and $t > 0$

$$M(z, w, a, b, qt) = M(Az, Bw, a, b, qt)$$

$$\geq \min \{ M(Sz, Tw, a, b, t), M(Az, Sz, a, b, t), M(Bw, Tw, a, b, t), M(Az, Tw, a, b, t) \}$$

$$\geq \min \{ M(z, w, a, b, t), M(z, z, a, b, t), M(w, w, a, b, t), M(z, w, a, b, t) \}$$

$$\geq M(z, w, a, b, t).$$

which implies that $M(z, w, a, b, qt) \geq M(z, w, a, b, t)$ and hence $z = w$.

This complete the proof of Theorem.

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